

IMPACT OF ADVERTISEMENT

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Abstract:

Advertising is actually brand building through effective communication and is essentially a service industry. It helps to create demand, promote marketing system and boost economic growth. The study analyse the growth of advertisement and how it is importance for an organization in every aspect. The research also reviewed many studies related to advertisement. The study also concludes that advertisement is capable of capturing the minds of customers for each and every product many brands of available in the market. At the time of shopping the customers must be able to recall the brand name of the product they want.

Key Words: Advertisement, Importance, Communication, Customer, Organization, Demand & Etc.,

Introduction:

Advertising is one of the aspects of mass communication. Advertising is actually brand building through effective communication and is essentially a service industry. It helps to create demand, promote marketing system and boost economic growth. With the expansion of large - scale production, growth of competition amongst the producers to capture markets has resulted in the invention of substitutes for almost all kinds of products. Effective advertising has become more indispensable. In the modern commercial world, all kinds of institution find advertising as a suitable means of publicity. Advertising has assumed more importance in the latter half of 19th century.

Advertisement:

The term advertising is derived from the Latin word *advertere* which means 'to turn' the attention. Every piece of advertising turns the attention of the readers or the listeners or the viewers or the onlookers towards a product or a service or an idea. Therefore, it can be said that anything that turn the attention to an article or a service or an idea might be well called as advertising.

Statement of the Problem:

The fiercely competitive pressures have led to the adoption of innovative marketing practices; worldwide promotional strategies have come to play a crucial role in the overall marketing mix. In recent times the growth and penetration of electronic media has tremendously increased. The marketers have attempted to create niche for their products and services. The market segmentation, though very difficulty, leads to increased market share using focused strategies. Since the trend is towards giving customers 'more value for less money'. The organizations are trying to economize in every area of operations. Consequently, the marketing professionals have been developing elaborate plans to get the maximum benefit of every rupee spend on advertising.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To understand the importance of advertisement
- ✓ To study the impact of advertisement on customer

Review of Literature:

David Deal (2000) has carried out studied entitled "The ability of branded in line games to built brand quality: An Exploratory Study" stated in that light of the relative failures of the early forms of online advertising, many markets are experimenting with advergaming as method of reaching the growing crowds that are turning to the internet for entertainment. While this new advertising media offers much promise, its effience has yet to be thoroughly proven, past research into interactivity, long exposure times and positive attitudes towards an advertisement thing that are typically garnered by advergaming, has shown that these attributes generates increases in brand equity for the advertised product. This relative abilities of advergaming and banner advertisement to generated recall, a common measure of brand equity. Advergaming were formed to generate significantly higher rates of recall, finding that supports the notion of their advertising effectiveness and the need for further research into this phenomenon.

Brad J. Bushman and Angelica M. Benacci (2002) have carried out a study entitled "Violence and sex impair memory for Television Advertisement" pointed that participants watched a violent. Sexually explicit, or neutral TV program that contained a ads participants recalled the advertised brands, they also, identified the advertised brands from slides of super markets shelves.

Nidhi Kotwal, Neelima Gupta and Arjee Devi (2002) have carried out a study entitled "Impact of T.V. advertisements on buying pattern of adolescent girls" This study revealed that television and advertising

together present a lethal combination and has become an integral part of modern society. The present study was conducted on 100 adolescent girls, studying in class 9th – 12th, to know the impact of T.V. advertisement of their buying pattern. It is the most convenient route to reach not only adult consumers but also the adolescents. Adolescents are manipulated by advertisement promise that the product will do something special for them which will transform their life.

Paul D. Bolls ; Darrel D. Muehling ; Kak Yoon (2003) in their study entitled that “The Effects of Television Commercial pacing on Viewers’ Attention and Memory”, pointed that the effects of advertising pacing on viewers’ voluntary and involuntary attention to an advertisement, as well as its effects on the recall of claim-related and non-claim-related components of the advertisement. Using a limited capacity model of information processing/retrieval as its theoretical base and physiologically oriented measures of attention, this study provided some evidence that fast-paced advertisements may have a positive effect on viewers’ involuntary attention towards an advertisement, but have little differential effect on their voluntary attention. Furthermore, it appeared that the enhanced involuntary attention gained through the use of fast-paced advertisement comes in the form of attention directed towards the non-claim elements of an advertisement as opposed to the message-based elements of the advertisement. The practical and theoretical implications of these findings are discussed.

Krishnan (2004) has carried out a study “Advertising rocks again, back in business urges that television used to be an expensive medium for small time advertisers a couple of years ago. But with the advent of a number of indigenous channels and increasing competition, it is becoming an affordable option for them today. And increase in competition makes it imperative for advertisers to use mass medium heavily and this explains the rise in the number of commercials on television.

Origin & Growth of Advertising:

Though advertising, in its present form, is the product of the current century, as a business force it is not a new tool. It has the longest history taking us back to the history of mankind and human civilization. The society fails to answer the question as to the exact age of advertising. It can be said that advertising began the moment the man discovered the art of communication. Historical documents and archaeological researches have confirmed the existence of advertising in the ancient times. Advertising by ‘word’ of mouth is probably the earliest form of advertising because, oral skills were developed well before reading and writing did. Advertising was given the commercial status the day he entered into the process of exchange. The colorful history of advertising can be divided into six clear-cut periods consisting of growth and development. Following is the period – wise evolution of advertising as a present-day powerful force.

History of Advertising:

1. Ancient Times-Up to 5th Century: Hammerbi ruled in Babylon 2,000 years before Christ. The artisan’s bakers, shoe-makers, green-grocers and other merchants were eager to exchange their goods for money and advertising came to their timely help. Selling goods in ancient times involved personal selling abilities. Merchants needed to identify their places with a symbol that told their trade, and so the shop signs were born. The merchants impressed upon the minds of consumers of the qualities of their wares which was done by the ‘hired criers’ or the ‘barkers’. Other form of communication was the ‘wall signs’. On the walls of the tall buildings near important gathering places were letter sign advertisement, entertainments, helped the location of taverns and goods for sale.

2. 5th to 8th Centuries: The period from 475 AD to 800 AD is referred to as ‘Dark Age’. This is the period that starts with the downfall of Roman Empire and ends with the coronation of Charlemagne. Advertising as a business force suffered a severe setback with the fall of Roman empire and one does not hear much of advertising in this dark age where the reading and writing were the prerogative of privileged few. Commerce and trade routes were drastically diminished. It did not mean that it dried up totally. It was furthered in the form of ‘voice’. Public barkers equipped with the horns and bells were capable of attracting the attention of consumers. Advertising was done either by human voice and or by hand executed signs and play cards.

3. 9th and 15th Centuries: The latter part of the Middle Age was a great and bold leap forward in human civilization and culture. Criers for the taverns were so numerous in Paris in the 13th century that they formed a union and were chartered by King Philip Augustus. These men developed a new gimmick of free samples. Printing originated in china and the oldest book printed was dated 868 AD. Johann Gutenberg laid the foundation of modern education by inventing a system of casting moveable type in 1438, in Mainz, Germany and printed the famous Bible in 1456. This rediscovery, in the West, together with an increase in education was essential to the growth of advertising. New methods of advertising were now available like printed posters, hand-bills, signs, pamphlets, books and newspapers.

4. 16th and 17th Centuries: During the 16th Century, newspapers were largest among the prints and these newspapers were in the form of news-letters. The first new-letter was started in 1622 in England. Latter half of the 16th century witnessed newspapers in the form of news-books and was common by the middle of 17th century. The outstanding features of 17th century were that there were special advertising periodicals. By 1675,

newspapers were published, excelled news books. By the end of 17th century, newspapers were well established in England undertaking advertising on a regular basis.

5. 18th and 19th Centuries: The age old principle of 'Caveat Emptor' ruled the transactions and hence the advertising that was resorted to was untruthful. That is why, the people did not believe totally in the advertisement message given. Buyers were to be cautious and diligent in buying the goods so advertised. The 19th century was marked by a new trend of brand advertising. Magazines-both weeklies and monthlies - started catching the imagination of the people by popularizing the brands. This is the period that welcomed window and counter displays, exhibitions and trade fairs.

6. The 20th Century: The current century is marked with the advent of two fascinating media of communication namely, radio and television. Americans have the credit of having these first. Radio ruled the scene from 1922 to 1947 and 1948 onwards, television took over. Radio advertising has an edge over print publicity that it is capable of reaching the millions of illiterate people as it is 'voice' advertising. Television could beat radio advertising with the visual effects. Television has been powerful means of advertising since 1950s and has grown in importance with its colour effects and is going to rule for few more decades to come. If these are the major indoor powerful media, the outdoor advertising has its own developments such as traveling displays, neon signs, sky-writing, in addition to the earlier means like posters, printed displays, painted displays and sandwich men.

Thus, the advertising industry started with 'barkers' and has culminated into a very powerful mass media of communication. It is an industry of multi-million rupees, employing millions, making the entire world of business to dance to its tunes. It has become a veritable boon to the world of business a boon of public relations and boon of public service. That is why, it has fortified its stay in future.

Advertising in India:

The history of advertising in India parallels the history of the Indian Press. The first issue of the first newspaper of the Indian subcontinent, was the 'Bengal Gazette' or the 'Calcutta General Advertiser', started by James Augustus Hicky on January 29, 1780. During the early years the newspapers announced births, deaths, appointments, arrival and departure of ships and sale of furniture. By the beginning of the 19th century the pattern of advertising revealed a definite change.

Even the daily newspapers announced themselves through advertisements in existing periodicals. The power of advertising increased rapidly with the growth in trade and commerce. By 1830, around three dozen newspapers and periodicals were being published on a regular basis from India. With the rise of new industries, advertising, even from British companies, increased. The growth of advertising in India is also linked to the Swadeshi movement (1920-1922), which gave impetus to Indian industries.

The first Indian ad agency, the Indian Advertising Agency, was launched in the very early years of the 20th century. On the other hand, B Dattaram & Co, located in Girgaum in Mumbai and launched in 1905, also claims to be the oldest existing Indian agency. This was followed by the launch of the Calcutta Advertising Agency in 1909. By the 1920s a number of Indian agencies were working from the major Indian cities, the most important being the Modern Publicity Company in Madras, Central Publicity Service in Bombay and Calcutta and the Oriental Advertising Agency in Tiruchirapalli.

In 1931, the first full-fledged Indian ad agency, the National Advertising Service, was established. During the post independence era, the advertising business was well on its way to growth and expansion. The Indian Society of Advertisers was formed in 1951 and in May 1958, the Society of Advertising Practitioners was established and advertising clubs came up in Bombay and Calcutta to promote higher standards of work. Market research and readership surveys led to further professionalisation of the advertising industry.

Television Rating Points, popularly known as TRP measurements, provided ad agencies with statistical data on consumer/ viewer likes and dislikes and helped them create effective media plans and ad campaigns. The introduction of multi-colour printing, improved printing machines and the development of commercial art gave the ad business a further boost. The advertising agencies expanded their services and this was due to the phenomenal growth in media. Besides selling space in newspapers and magazines, they began to offer artworks, organization of fairs and exhibitions and market research.

Some Advertising Terms to Remember:

Tagline: A tagline is a creative, often witty, ad slogan that helps people remember a particular product. Can you think of any popular taglines?

Brand: Brand is the name of a product or service that is very easily recognizable. People buy the product because of the brand name. Some famous brands are Dettol, Pepsi cola, Parle G, Hawkins pressure cooker, Bajaj scooter, Yamaha motorbikes, Cadburys chocolate, Ponds soap, Sunsilk shampoo, Band Aid, Dalda, Hamam soap, Lifebouy soap.

Campaign: An advertisement campaign is a series of advertisement messages that share a single idea and theme which together make up an advertisement strategy for a product, service, or institution. Advertising campaigns appear in different media across a specific time frame. An example of an advertising campaign is the 'Jago

Grahak Jago' (wake up, consumer) campaign initiated by the government of India to create consumer awareness and protect the rights of the consumer across the country.

Target Audience: Target audience or target group is the primary group of people that something, usually an advertising campaign, is aimed at. A target audience can be people of a certain age group, gender, marital status, etc. (example: teenagers, females, single people, etc.) A certain combination, like men from twenty to thirty is often a target audience. Other groups, although not the main focus, may also be interested. Without knowing your target audience, advertising and the selling of a particular product can become difficult and expensive.

The Ethical Aspect of Advertising:

Many of the ethical aspects of advertising, border on and interact with both the social and legal, consideration of the advertising process. The ethical aspect of advertising mainly falls in three areas:

- ✓ Truth in Advertising: Avoid the false or misleading statements in an advertisement.
- ✓ Advertising to Children: Children are inexperienced consumers and an easy preference for the sophisticated persuasiveness of advertisers. Advertising influences children's demands for everything from toys to snack foods. So, the advertisement should not create a child parent environment.
- ✓ Advertising Controversial Product: The issue of advertising controversial products like tobacco, alcoholic beverages, gambling and lotteries etc are more complex. While making advertisement for these products, it should not persuade the consumers for too much of their consumption.
- ✓ Advertising Effects
- ✓ Advertising serves four functions in business and society. It is a marketing tool, a transmitter of information, an economic stimulant, and a purveyor of values. As part of marketing, advertising communicates information about goods and services. It also adds product value by creating enduring "brands." Successful marketing campaigns stimulate demand and subsequent economic growth. But because advertising is so pervasive, there are concerns regarding its effects on society.
- ✓ Societal Impact: Among other concerns, critics of advertising believe it promotes materialism and encourages consumers to buy products they do not need. They also argue that advertising manipulates, perpetuates stereotypes, preys on children, is used to sell harmful products, and contribute to a variety of other social ills. Those who defend advertising note that advertising is merely a tool, a form of communication that can be used for good as well as bad purposes, depending upon the advertiser. It is used not only to sell products, but also to gain donations for charities, as well as for other causes. Indeed, it is an enormous industry, and it frequently is defended by noting its economic contribution to society.
- ✓ Economic Impact: Advertising is a global industry. In the United States alone, over \$290 billion was spent on advertising during 2007. U.S. advertising revenues have accounted for approximately 2% of the GDP since 1950. Procter & Gamble, the leading advertiser, alone spent \$5 billion during 2007. These expenditures affect everyone involved in advertising, including the advertisers, their agencies, and the media companies that provide advertisers with an audience. In addition to the money poured into the economy, for the free market to work properly consumers must be sovereign, able to freely make informed decisions in a competitive marketplace. Advertising is necessary to provide that information and enhance competition. Furthermore, advertising reduces the time and cost for consumers to gather this information.
- ✓ Law and Ethics: Because this is a communication industry, the First Amendment of the U.S. Constitution limits government's role in regulating advertising. There are, however, regulatory standards imposed by government to ensure fair competition and protect consumers from deception. The Federal Trade Commission (FTC) is the primary federal agency governing the advertising industry. The FTC is focused on eliminating advertising deception. The Federal Communication Commission (FCC), too, is involved through its oversight of broadcast media. In its role, the FCC maintains a certain level of decency and decorum, having the authority to fine broadcasters for violating mandated standards. The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) also plays a role, monitoring claims regarding food and drugs. In addition, industry has created a major self-regulatory mechanism designed to supplement government regulation. The National Advertising Review Council (NARC) accepts and reviews consumer complaints about advertising. It has created a process for charging advertisers with violating accepted standards, judging their compliance, and enforcing subsequent corrective actions.
- ✓ Account Management: Account executives are the interface between the agency and client. Within the agency they represent the needs of the client, pursuing the services necessary to provide adequate support. This includes working with the client to develop business objectives for the agency to meet. Once the agency has developed an advertising plan to meet those objectives, account management must sell the client on the merits of that plan.
- ✓ Research & Account Planning: Effective advertising is usually based on solid research. Both quantitative and qualitative research are used to provide information about product use and

performance. Agencies conduct any necessary research through a research or account planning (also called strategic planning) department. Account Planning is a newer twist on traditional research departments, and it is seen as representing the voice of the consumer. In this capacity, the Account Planning team provides consumer insights to the Creative team regarding how the brand is used and perceived, to help determine the best way to approach the consumer.

- ✓ Creative: The Creative Department is responsible for actually designing the advertisement. The “creatives” work with the Account Management team to understand the business objectives, and with the Account Planners to understand how consumers interact with the brand. They then develop a “creative concept” that will drive the campaign, which one or more art directors and copy writers then use to guide them in making the advertisements. Ultimately, the client must approve their work before it goes into production.
- ✓ Production: Once a campaign is approved, the Creative Department relies upon the Production Department to produce the final ad. Production departments are responsible for recommending production companies and directors, negotiating contracts, and overseeing all production budgets. They work closely with the Creative Teams to ensure that the final ads meet client expectations.
- ✓ Media Planning & Buying: For advertisements to work, they must be seen by a number of prospective customers. The Media Department must develop a plan that delivers the necessary consumer exposure within the confines of the client’s budget. It recommends the media that should be used and the schedule to be followed to achieve each client’s objectives. Because budget is the ultimate constraint, media prices are crucial to planning. Agencies that secure the best pricing can deliver more powerful plans. Consequently, agencies have arisen that do nothing but media buying. While most advertising agencies have maintained media planning departments, these specialty media buying agencies have assumed a greater role in recent years.

Conclusion:

In the modern day the wants of people are progressively increasing. They are in need of many products. To fulfill the customers many manufacturers enter into the market. Most of the manufacturers give advertisement to make awareness among the public. The advertisement is capable of capturing the minds of customers for each and every product many brands of available in the market. At the time of shopping the customers must be able to recall the brand name of the product they want. So the manufacturers must keep in mind while making advertisement how to attract customers. They are many media for making advertisement of them; television is the most prominent medium of advertisement that capture the minds of customer, because it is presented with audio and video facilities.

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